

5G in Rural Forest enables Real Time decision support and new Remote Operation solutions

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Abstract: A lot of attention has traditionally been given to digitalization of smart cities and urban areas. However, bridging the digital divide for the rural areas has become necessary to exploit the full economic growth from new technologies since many industries also belong to the countryside. This paper introduces novel insights into use cases from the forest industry and the perceived impact from innovations activated from technologies such as the fifth-generation mobile technology (5G) and Internet of Things (IoT). An agile methodology is followed developing the forest use cases to handle the risk and uncertainty within this domain. After interviews with stakeholders from the forest value chain we found that digitalization of the forest value chain is necessary. We also found three distinct use cases with different scenarios where premium cellular network (5G) connection can make an impact. The potential impact dimensions were identified and operationalized in three groups: business, user/society, and environment. Our findings will set the scene for the forthcoming specification of the use case requirements and the validation of Proof of Concept's (PoC's) during the next step in our agile methodology. Our work is funded through Horizon Europe program COMECT and PoC's trial results from the Norwegian forest living lab will be published at a later stage.

Keywords: Telecommunication systems, 5G, IoT, Rural areas, Connected Forests, Economic/Social/Environmental impact

I. INTRODUCTION

The elimination of the digital divide in rural areas is necessary to fully exploit the impact of digitalization [1]. This will aid the creation of a clever countryside and satisfy consumers with internet access (fiber and 5G), serving local businesses such as manufacturing, outdoor recreation, green energy production, and farming, enabling anchor institutions to work well - education, healthcare, and first responders [2]. The European Commission have a long term vision for how connectivity can be a key element in revitalizing local

communities and make them more sustainable by 2040 through better business opportunities for the businesses, innovations within agriculture, keeping and bringing families back to the countryside thanks to remote working, telemedicine, and online services [3]. This is also the background for the COMECT project funded by EU (Horizon Europe), 19 partners from academia, research, industry, and SMEs from five different EU countries are organized around five different living labs, agriculture, viticulture, forest, live-stock, and olive farming [4]. The objective is to provide connectivity to these rural communities with a cost effective and environmentally friendly solution [4].

The telecom operator Telenor is involved in the forest living lab in Norway together with Klosser Innovation, the Inland Norway University of Applied Sciences, and other stakeholders. With this backdrop, we raise the following research question: *What are the most relevant use cases in the forest industry where 5G will have a major impact?* A preliminary state-of-the-art review uncover some research findings related to single steps of the forest value chain: satellite-based positioning of automatic harvesting (logging) machines in Poland [5], 5G based remote steering of robots bringing timber from logging site to closest road for transport to sawmill in Sweden [6] [7] and drone based data collection/forest management in Lithuania using cellular 5G connections [8]. Through our research approach we aim to achieve a more holistic overview of the value chain and at the same time offer qualified selection of use case scenarios through in-depth interviews with stakeholders throughout the forest ecosystem. Moreover, we aim to offer insight into how 5G and IoT technologies can enable innovations in a co-creative and agile way and the perceived impact of these innovations with respect to business, environment, and user/society aspects.

II. 5G, ECOSYSTEMS AND AGILE INNOVATION

The fifth-generation mobile network technology (5G) is expected to provide business opportunities in many industry verticals, as it introduces lower latency, higher capacity, and massive deployment of IoT devices (1 million devices per square kilometer) compared to current 4G technology [9]. Significant economic and social value is expected to be generated from use case innovations activated by 5G. According to a study by HIS Markit [10], \$13.2 trillion in global economic value will be made possible by 2035, generating 22.3 million jobs in the 5G global value chain alone. The number of devices connected to Internet will be 125 billion in 2030, a vast jump from current situation with 31 million devices, hence a major opportunity for gaining new revenue sources for multiple ecosystem actors, including telecom operators. The IoT applications offered to smart city and urban communities outnumber the offerings to rural communities, and are mostly related to transport/traffic, water level and air quality monitoring [11].

Business ecosystems refers to systems of independent actors who together provide a comprehensive solution for customer or end user [12]. According to Man [13] we also find value proposition ecosystems where the actors actively engage in an agile co-creation process around a single joint value proposition with a client. The Triple Helix model describes how innovations are created in collaboration between three major actors - industrial companies, academia/universities, and the public/government. The ecosystem health is measured by its degree of performance (financial metrics) [14], robustness (survive disruptions) and diversity [15] (create innovative niche products and services). Startups and small and medium sized companies (SMEs) are attractive partners and suppliers for large firms due to their size, focus, business specification, entrepreneurial persons, and speed. Telecom operators have traditionally organized innovation in a closed context to ensure control over their intellectual property and the commercialization process towards customers and the market. However, the current lack of revenue growth [16] has forced them to look beyond the traditional network connectivity services, through collaboration with partners in new industry verticals. Open innovation relates to innovation processes where knowledge and innovation develops between different actors - in other companies as well as in publicly funded research environments [17].

Design thinking and lean start/agile way of work are state of the art bottom-up innovation process principles and methodologies applied in industries and businesses today that helps explore and tackle research-based problems that often are ill-defined or unknown. According to Cooper [18] and Ries [19] co-creation and development with users and customers avoids doing unnecessary redesign due to lack of feedback on prototypes/minimum viable products (MPVs) from

stakeholders/actor groups external to the innovation project, hence gets the desired product to customers' hands faster.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Figure 1 illustrates the agile methodology applied for studying the COMMECT forest living lab use cases [19] [20].

Fig. 1: Agile development methodology

- 1) *Needs*: Map needs and problems for stakeholders in the forest value chain. Collecting feedback and data through desk top studies, workshops, interviews, surveys etc.
- 2) *Solution*: Design prototypes of possible solutions mitigating the problems identified. Specify supporting test infrastructure set-ups.
- 3) *Test*: prototypes designed based on problems Perform pilots using 5G test infrastructure, e.g. 5G network on wheels mobile trailer or drones with antennas mounted.
- 4) *Learn*: Evaluate results from prototype tests with respect to performance, socio-economy, and environment impact. Input to revisions of solutions and tests set-ups

A use case describes the ways that stakeholders want to use a system (technology, process, device) to perform a task or activity and hence reach an overall goal [21]. The latter involves the validation of the perceived impact for these stakeholders. In the context of the COMMECT Forest living Lab, we see a use case as a concrete situation or event, where one or alternative solutions may be applied, and where identified persons hold stakes in the situation/event. In this paper we refer to this using the term “use case solution”. In the early stages of the Living lab development, an early MVP (minimum viable product) of the solution is presented for feedback and revisions.

This paper focuses on the initial agile development phase, detailing the forest use cases where 5G enabled solutions can make a difference. This lays the foundation for requirements and design of innovative solutions and validation of the perceived impact for stakeholders identified. Table 1 shows the data sources for identifying use cases needs and impact.

TABLE 1. DESCRIPTION OF DATA SOURCES

Method	Information sources	Year
Desk top study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Study of forest industry's business and technology challenges preparing EU/ COMMECT research project application 	Spring 2021
Workshop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop with stakeholders from all parts of the forest value chain in Norway 	Autumn 2022
Interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interview (Teams) with single stakeholders for the forest value chain Interview (Teams) with PM from other Forest research and innovation program 	Spring 2023

Initially a desk top study of the forestry industry in Norway was performed. After the COMMECT project application was granted, workshop and interviews with the core stakeholders were performed for the south-east region (Inland County):

- *Forest owners' associations* offer small and large forest owners services throughout all the value chain phases and assist forest owners with certification, technology, economy, real estate development etc.
- *Suppliers/vendors of forest machines* for the cleaning, logging, and bringing forward of logs to trucks for further transport to sawing mills.
- *Organization offering education and training* in the forestry sector, planning, economy, ecology and certification, forest operations and techniques etc.
- *Provider of third-party (wireless) technology* for exploitation of production data from the forest machines
- *Sawing and planning mills* producing sawn timber for further processing and resale. Planning products are most often interior and exterior panel as well as adjusted timber.
- *Machine entrepreneurs/operators* perform the forest thinning and logging for forest owner and leasing forest machines from the machine vendors/suppliers.

The workshop lasted for one day with roughly 20 stakeholders participating. The objective was to uncover 1) most important problems/challenges which digitalization/5G could help solve for the forest value chain (and how these were solved today), 2) the type of impact digitalization was expected to offer (business, safety environmental etc.) and 3) which stakeholders in value chain were the most important ones affected by the problems and challenges? The follow up interviews lasted for up to 2 hours on Teams. Here the aim was to understand their role in the value chain and the collaboration with other ecosystem actors. Each stakeholder was also asked to separate their pain points on a short-, medium- and long-term horizon and assess features for potential mitigating solutions and technologies. Applying multiple data sources corresponds to the triangulation principle described [22]. The selected companies for workshop and interviews are referred to as strategic selection [22]. The data were analysed per case in addition to description of survey and interview statements. Confirming minutes from interviews improves use case reliability and validity [23].

IV. FINDINGS

An overview of the forest value chain and results from the collected data on main stakeholder needs and challenges is presented in figure 2 below.

Fig. 2: Forest value chain and use cases.

The forest value chain consists of different phases spanning over 60-80 years (from planting to logging) following transport and sawing of the logs for further processing of wood products:

- **Planting:** New trees are planted right after logging. In 2021, 39,4 million trees were planted in Norway, up 70.5% compared with the decade before. [24]. Planting is mostly manual labor, and putting the plants correctly into the ground and in the right place is crucial. 15% of the plants die after first 1-2 years, it is weather dependent, most often due to temperature and drought as well as beetles attack.
- **Care:** Caring for young forests with brush cutters, removing forest/deciduous trees around planted trees, or sown trees sowing too tightly. A lot of work is not possible. Here it is important to invest in the right trees, i.e to select those that have the greatest chance of survival. Forest care is also mostly performed with manual labor.
- **Thinning:** Smaller forestry machines take out trees that are least suitable to use in premium products such as planks. Thinning trees ends up to lots of wood (chipboard). Often the same type of forest machines as used for logging in general, but smaller in size. It is important to have an experienced and/or very good machine-operator because he/she must pick out the bad trees according to his/her own assessment. Knowing more about the quality of the single tree in advance would be valuable.
- **Logging:** Takes place according to specifications from the buyer of forest/sawmills (length, and "quality"). Loggings are done using machines, e.g log harvesters from John Deere. Later, different machine pulls the trees to the trucks waiting at the forest road. Fertilization of forests usually occurs every 10 to 20 years before logging by helicopter (accurate), forest-walking machines and by hand. It increases the volume of trees, i.e increased harvest value.
- **Transport:** After logging, the timber is transported to the sawmills (usually by truck, alternatively by train or boat). The logs are measured (the bulk of logs on a trailer) at fixed autonomous measuring stations throughout Norway on their way to the sawmill.
- **Sawing:** At the sawmill the logs are cut in different shapes of wooden planks for the buyer/user. The buyers are most often large chain of timber resellers. Before the logs are cut, there is a third measurement of length.

The overall interest from the stakeholders is the need for a more digitalized value chain with the opportunity to share data across and amongst themselves. This can enable more efficient, safe, and environmentally friendly operations. The latter refers to easier management and reporting that the activities are in line with Co2 requirements. It is expected that everyone must follow certification such as the PEFC (Program for the Endorsement of Forest Certification) [25], otherwise they will be banned from the industry. Beyond the need for digitalization, we find three distinct use cases. They are relevant for multiple phases, but are mostly related to the logging phase:

UC1: Remote operation and safety: Recruitment to the forest industry is challenging, often because of safety issues for the operators being alone inside or outside the forest machines during the period when cutting the logs. With no or little network coverage, communication options are few or non-existing. Remote steering (using AR/VR tools) of these operations in relation to logging activities (cutting and bringing logs from site to trucks at nearby forest roads) will mitigate the risk of operator injuries. Current lack of real time services provides delays in production and is not cost efficient. Furthermore, remote operations via 4G mobile communication are challenging due to its high latency and low throughput value for real time control.

UC2: Decision Support and positioning: A system that provides the forest owner and machine entrepreneur/operator with real time data enabling them to improve the decision-making processes. This will improve the opportunity for the operator to better select (using VR/AR tools) the logs to thin/care or cut, hence improve revenues for the stakeholders. Such information can be presented to the operator through real time streaming from cameras. The digitalization should start from the planting of the tree. The position of the tree stands (position) and its health condition is lacking to be monitored using IoT devices. The more one knows about the single tree (profile/position) before logging it, will also reduce the incidents of cutting rare biotopes (and destroying cultural monuments), in addition to enabling smart routing, hence reducing the fuel consumption and Co2 emission along with reduced degradation of the soil/forest floor.

UC3: Real time situational awareness: In situations where accidents and injuries of the operators or other major disasters such as forest fires, floods, landslides etc. there is a need for real time situational awareness. Applying drones (with mounted 5G antennas) can be used to distribute real time video to e.g smart phones or other devices of emergency personnel's (police, ambulance, forest fighters, municipality) will enable such a common situational awareness that is necessary to handle the situation effectively. The objective is to secure the operations of the core forest living lab stakeholders initially described, but in this use case we will need to involve stakeholders beyond these ones for further need assessment and trials.

In table 2 an overview of the perceived impact related to the three use cases is presented. Here we have also included the

telecommunication provider as a forest ecosystem actor [12] in relation to the technological performance/impact. For the societal impact we also address the municipality/community. For UC1 (Remote operation and safety), the impact is related to increased value creation through more efficient machine operations, e.g., cost reduction through less forest machine maintenance downtime. Moreover, increased recruitment and improved working conditions and safety for operators as well as less Co2 emission from less transport etc. Impacted stakeholders are forest owners and their associations in addition to the operators. For UC2 (Decision support and positioning) the impact is related to increased profit (less cost and more revenues) through optimal thinning and logging operations, documentation, and differentiation of timber to be sawed and further processed from bulk, i.e., length and volume to quality and price differentiation. Furthermore, destroying biotopes and unnecessary intervention of forest grounds (tracks) is also avoided. Finally, a more comprehensive production according to environmental claims is possible. The involved stakeholders are the forest owners/associations and the entrepreneurs/machine operators.

TABLE 2. IMPACT DIMENSIONS AND TECHNOLOGICAL ENABLERS FOR FOREST LL UC's

Impact/Enabler	Dimensions	UC 1	UC 2	UC 3
Business impact	Revenue increase	X	X	
	Cost reduction	X	X	
	Time saved	X		
	Less penalties/goodwill	X	X	
User and society impact	Improved certification	X	X	X
	Improved safety (HSE)	X	X	X
	Better user experience	X	X	
	Increased accessibility	X	X	
Environmental impact	Increased quality of life	X	X	X
	Better crisis management			X
	Reduced Co2 emission	X	X	
	Less abrasion on terrain	X	X	X
Techno-logical enablers	Portfolio of old/new flora	X	X	
	Saving species diversity	X	X	X
	Saving culture heritage	X	X	X
	Reduced latency	X	X	X
	Increased coverage	X	X	X
	Increased IoT density		X	
	Increased data rate/speed	X	X	X
	Increased reliability	X		X

For UC 3 (Real time situational awareness) the impact is related to improved safety and reduced accidents, forest fires etc. during operations. The municipality is also highly relevant beyond the core value chain stakeholders, improving the capabilities for crisis management throughout the region and since they hold the rescue, police, and ambulance resources necessary. VR/AR tools can also be applied in this use case.

V. DISCUSSION

Today, a significant portion of the global population is still not connected to the Internet. Among the 27 countries in Europe the mean broadband coverage (5G) was 65,8%. However, for the rural areas in the same countries, the mean coverage was

only 34,7%. [26]. Common for these regions is that they have lower income levels, unfavorable demographics, higher unemployment rates and weaknesses in skills and human capital, compared to urban areas, hence less attractive for commercial development and growth [4].

The findings from the use case studies indicates that 5G and IoT based innovative solutions can help mitigating the lack of digitalization and other challenges the forest value chain stakeholders struggle with today. The value chain in the Norwegian forest living lab is fairly the same as it was 50 years ago. Sawmills are good at extracting the maximum value of the log they process, and the greatest efficiency gains and revenue opportunities are found in the earlier value chain phases. Telenor Sweden and Ericsson shows how remote management and control of forestry machines in a separate step of the value chain can be performed using applying 5G technology [7]. This is related to bringing the timber from the site where it is logged to the awaiting trucks to transport them to sawmills. This paper points out how other steps of the value chain also can gain impact from applying 5G/IoT technology-based solutions. The dimensions applied for business impact (CAPEX and OPEX reduction, less production workforce, revenue increase, faster time to market etc.), user and societal impact (user experience, health and safety, inclusiveness, social justice, ethics, trust and privacy, and 5G technology (increased coverage, reliability, latency and slicing) are similar to the ones found in other 5G research and innovation projects [27]. Nesse et. al [28] [29] recommends simultaneous validation of business value, social acceptance and technology performance starting from the initial trials of MVP/PoC's. Moreover, the three impact dimension groups should be validated equally important.

Environmental impact dimensions are related to different activities executed by the value chain stakeholders. The Norwegian PEFC (Program for the Endorsement of Forest Certification) forest standard was revised in 2015. In practice all forest properties in operation after year 2000 are comprehended by this certification which contains 27 claim/requirements towards the management and governance of the forest [25]. Firstly, the claims are related to interventions in the forest such as logging, wastage and pollution, tire tracks, planting and distribution of tree species, cultural heritage, preparation of the grounds, life course of trees, pesticides, and use of fertilization. Secondly, the claims are directed towards governance and planning, such as workers and their safety, transport roads, conservation of the forests, native population rights, recreation, preservation of genes (trees). Thirdly, PEFC forward particularly environmental values such as conservation of key biotopes/habitat, respect for owls and other falconiforms, water/wet/mash areas protection and fire influenced forest.

An agile methodology is applied to better handle the risk and uncertainty when introducing novel technology like 5G within this domain. A living lab is a user-centered, open innovation ecosystem [30] [31]. Moreover, it is user driven, carried out in realistic real-life setting, with rapid prototyping and testing, and short time to market. The concept is also based on a systematic integration of user co-creation approach during the research and innovation processes. This involves exploration, experimentation and evaluation of innovative ideas, scenarios, concepts, and related technological artefacts in real life use cases.

The prerequisite for extracting this impact is the access to broadband connectivity (5G/4G) as well as solutions for real time video streaming from drones, access to maps and 3D models of the forest and access to accurate positioning, improved user experience through Virtual reality (VR) and Augmented reality (AR) headsets etc. Today, connectivity solutions that offer real time transmission of video and updating 3D data models to rural sites limits best practices for UC1, UC2 and UC 3. Hence, 5G technology can contribute to climate change mitigation and a more sustainable forest industry. The 5G networks are approx. 90 % more energy efficient per traffic unit than 4G networks with more data bits per kilowatt of energy than any previous wireless technology generation [32]. Increased coverage and new features and capabilities that the fifth-generation mobile network technology can offer enables decision support for smart routes and remote steering options that will reduce the need for the operators to travel, Co2 emission will be limited to an optimum, avoid destruction of cultural heritage site and rare biotopes etc.

The forest living lab studied in Norway has characteristics of open innovation and business/value proposition ecosystems. There are multiple stakeholders, but it is too premature for any stakeholder taking on the lead as a keystone [33] in the digitalization process. Introducing the public agencies and the municipality will also include similarities with the triple helix model [34]. The forthcoming keystone and other actors will jointly contribute to the ecosystem's health, and thus affect both own and other players' success including business models that adds value and profitability for the whole ecosystem.

VI. CONCLUSION

It is time to bridge the digital divide between urban and rural areas of Europe. This will make the countryside more lucrative for current and new businesses, improve the quality of life of the citizens and secure more efficient production of social services offered by the municipalities. 5G and IoT are enabling technologies for digitalization and provides an opportunity for telecom operators for future growth, mitigating the decline in revenues from their connectivity service and subscriptions. The aim of this paper was to provide insight into use cases, stakeholders, value chain and potential impact from digitalization through 5G of the forest industry in Norway.

Using an agile approach, we unveiled three major use cases where 5G/IoT can make difference, i.e., have financial, user/societal, and environmental impact. Our research findings are limited to one geographical area and a set of stakeholders in Norway. Further studies are needed to confirm the use cases requirements in a broader context as well as revisiting the impact dimensions for validation of forthcoming PoC trials. Moreover, the roles and positions the telecom operator may take in the forest business ecosystem, and the design of joint business and governance models is also necessary to uncover going forward.

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